

SOCIAL NETWORKING AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: COLLEGE OF EDUCATION STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The study examined students' perception of influence of social networking on academic performance in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. Descriptive research design was used to conduct the study while data were collected through questionnaire. The study involved a total of 145 participants who were randomly selected. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze data collected. Findings revealed that most of the students have access to social networking sites and that majority prefer WhatsApp and Facebook. Similarly, students spend more time on social networking at the expense of individual learning. Consequently, social networking negatively influenced students' academic performance. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that different education software should be made available and accessible to students and the use of social networking in teaching and learning should be encouraged.

Introduction

The evolution of information technology has dramatically changed all aspect of our lives including teaching and learning. This has eased the process of exploring wide range of knowledge both formal and informal. The use of modern information technology has continued to increase especially among young people (Magwa, 2013). Nowadays, the use of various information technology devices such as smart phone, laptop etc has become part of students' life. However, two-third of the world's internet population visits social networking site (SNS), Blogging sites, etc. Social networking sites (SNS) are online communities of internet users who want to communicate with other users about areas of mutual interest, whether from a personal, business or academic perspective (Ainni et al., 2015).

The use of social networking site (SNS) has transformed the world into a global village where distance is no longer a barrier in communication. It provides effective communication among different people regardless of the distance. Also, it makes sharing of information in forms of documents, pictures, audio, videos and other materials easier. Online social networking sites

such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, TikTok, YouTube among others focus on building and reflecting social association among people who share interest and or activities. SNS are being used by the teachers and students as a communication tool. Also, SNS forums and groups are used to extend classroom deliberations. WhatsApp, Twitter and Facebook are most common used teachers to communicate announcement and information to their students. It is a bidirectional process as students too are using these media to ask questions and share comments with their teachers. The most popular age bracket of Nigerians on Facebook is under the age of 25 with over 5.6million Nigerians in the demography. Both Secondary School and University students use SNS not only to stay in touch with existing friends and make new ones but also to exchange information about classes, concerts parties, or any other matter of interest. Thus students spend more hours on social websites (Tafesse, 2022). In Nigeria, a recent report shows that WhatsApp is most popular social networking platform among internet users, as over 94% users, followed by Facebook, 88.8%, Facebook Messenger, 69.9%, Twitter, 61.2% and TikTok, 57.4% (Sasu, 2022).

As such there is no doubt that social media has gained wider acceptability and becoming the most important communication tool especially among students in tertiary institutions.

Al-Rahmi and Othman (2013), argued that among various unique distractions of every single generation, Facebook remains a major distraction of current generation. All these result into students blaming the social Networking sites for their steady decrease in Grade Point Average ((GPA). There is a derivation, distraction and divided attention between social networking activities and their academic works. It is observed that students devote more attention to social networking than they do to their studies. Therefore, this study attempts to determine the influence of social networking site (SNS) on the academic performances of Primary Education students in Kwara state college of education. Specifically, the study examined level of accessibility, frequency of use and influence of social networking.

Literature Review

Concept of Social Networking

Social networking is the communication with people who share interests using a websites site also referred to as SNS, are viewed as online communities of internet. Social Networking site also referred to as SNS, are viewed as online communities of internet users who want to communicate with other users about area of mutual interest, Whether from a personal business or academic perspective. De Andrea et al., (2012), revealed that modern social networking sites are web-based service that enable individuals to construct a public or semipublic profile with a bounded system, articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, view and transverse their list of connections and those made by other users within the system, although the native and nomenclature of these website are social forums or ways of communicating directly with other people socially and in media. Among the vast variety of online tools which are available for communication is social networking sites (SNS) which have become the most attractive tools for connecting people throughout the world. The major characteristics of social networking sites are; user based, interactive, community-driven, relationships and emotion over content (English & Duncen-Howell, 2008; Abraham,

Adehisil & Bethlehem, 2018).

One of the major usefulness of social networking is the ability to foster socialization among the users particularly the youth. They often use social networking websites to stay in touch with friends and relatives. Most youths tend to visit these SNS daily to get daily news information about happenings within and outside the country. Also, social networking is an avenue for a citizen to bring the attention of the government to what is needed in their environment or by suggesting the government since it will not be possible for one to go to the office of whoever is in authority (Ainni et al., 2015; Kulidtod & Pasagui, 2017).

Social Networking and Student's Academic Performance

Social networking sites such as Facebook, 2go, WhatsApp have positive influence on students' performance through online group discussion, interactions, on-line tutorials and different group studies. Studies have shown that students are socially connected with each other for sharing their daily learning experience and do conversation on several topics. Also, it has been argued that extra curriculum activities and academic activities are not enough to satisfy some students, those who have suffered social networking isolation. This shows that social networks are beneficial for the students as it contributes in their leaning experiences as well as in their academic life. Students especially at higher level of learning can function collaboratively through exploring the opportunities given by online social atmosphere to resolve certain academic issues with their peers (English, & Duncen-Howell, 2008; Al-Rahmi & Othman, 2013; Kulidtod & Pasagui, 2017).

However, there are some risks associated with the use of social network, there have been reports regarding its negative effects on students' academic performance. There is a poor effect and influence when the media is over used in such a way that does not improve learning or its process. Student who reported internet caused school work problem were found to have spent more hours online, stay update, get less sleep and miss classes. Poor academic performances were reported by students who make use of the social network sites such as, whatsapp, facebook, 2go and other for real time social activities such as instant messaging (IM) and chartrooms. Al-Rahmi and

Othman (2013) noted that these social uses are what hold students captive, especially late at night. As a result of too much time spent on the network daily, students are now used to abbreviating words such as “d” (for “the), Hbd (for Happy birthday), kk, (for okay), IJN (for in Jesus Name) etc, which reflects in their notes, assignments school work and even examinations thereby leading to poor performances

Method

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine the influence of social

networking on students' academic performance. The target population of the study comprised all Primary Education students of Kwara state College of Education, Ilorin for 2021/2022 academic session. A total of 145 students were randomly selected as sample of the study through the use of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. Data were collected using structured questionnaire developed by the researchers. The reliability of the instrument was determined with the use of Cronbach Alpha statistical tool which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.76. While descriptive statistics was used to analyze data.

Presentation of Result

Table 1: Accessibility and Preference of Social Networking sites

Response	Accessibility				Preference	
	Yes		No		F	%
	F	%	F	%		
2GO	102	70.34	43	29.66	34	23.45
WhatsApp	128	88.28	17	11.72	65	44.83
Facebook	123	84.83	22	15.17	46	31.72
Total					145	100

Table 1 shows that 70.34 % of respondents have access to 2go, 88.28% have access to WhatsApp while 84.83 have access to Facebook. Similarly,

23.45% preferred 2go, 44.83% of respondents preferred whatsapp while 31.72% preferred facebook.

Table 2: Frequency of use of Social Networking among Students

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very often	76	52.41
Often	45	31.03
Seldom	17	11.72
Very seldom	7	4.83
Total	145	100

From the table 2, 52.41% of the respondents use social networking very often, 31.03% of the respondents use SNS often, while 11.72%

seldomly use SNS and 4.83% use social networking very seldom.

Table 3: Social Networking Influence on Students' Academic Performance

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Positive	56	38.62
Negative	82	56.55
Neutral	7	4.83
Total	145	100

Table 3 shows that 38.62% of the respondents are of the view that social networking has positive influence on students' academic performance, 56.55% of respondents are of perception that SNS influence on students' academic performance is negative while 4.83% are neutral.

Discussion of Findings

The study examined the influence of social networking on students' academic performance in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. Data were collected from 145 respondents through questionnaire and analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics method. Findings reveals that majority of participants have access to 2go, WhatsApp and Facebook (70.34%, 88.28% and 84.83% respectively). And that many of the students prefer WhatsApp to Facebook and Facebook to 2go (44.83%, 31.72% and 23.45%). Also, result shows that students spend most of their times on social networking sites than individual learning (83.45%). Additionally, finding shows that social networking has both positive and negative influence on students' academic performance. However, its negative influence (56.55%) outweighs the positive influence (38.62%). These findings agreed with previous studies (Ahmed & Qazi, 2011; Apeanti & Danso, 2014; Abraham et al., 2018; Tafesse, 2022)

Conclusion

Based on the results, the following conclusions were drawn: Students of Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin have access to social networking sites such as 2go, WhatsApp, Facebook etc. Also, students spend more time on social networking than individual learning. Furthermore, social networking was found to have negative influence on students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the finding and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. More educational software should be made available and accessible to students to enhance learning outcome.
2. The students should be encouraged to spend less time on social networking and more time on individual and group learning activities.
3. The use of social networking platforms in teaching and learning should be encouraged among teachers.

Suggestion for Further Studies

Further studies are suggested to investigate the influence of social networking on students' academic performance based on gender (male & female) and student ability (high, average & low). Also, the use of inferential statistics method for data analysis is recommended for using in further research.

Funding

(TETFund/DESS/COE/ILORIN/ARJ/1)
"TETFund Projects 2019-2021"

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